

Insect pests of rice in the Imphal Valley of Manipur, India.

Pest and year of severity	Family	Economic status	Damage ^a
Stem borer, 1979 <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walk)	Pyralidae	Major pests in dry season. Collectively, become major in upland rice.	9.7% DH at preflowering and 16.7% at postflowering, 10 Apr 1979.
<i>S. innotata</i> (Walk)	Pyralidae		
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walk)	Pyralidae		
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walk)	Noctuidae		
Gall midge, 1981–82 <i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Cecidomyiidae	Major pest in the main season, particularly in late transplanted rice.	11.1% SS on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
Green leafhopper, 1980–82 <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Dist.)	Cicadellidae	Major pests in the main season.	7.0 GLH/5 sweeps on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
<i>N. nigropictus</i> (Stal)	Cicadellidae		
Leafroller, 1979–83 <i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guen.)	Pyralidae	Major pest in the main season	22.5 LR/m ² on 8 Jul 1981 transplanting
Caseworm, 1980–82 <i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> Guen.	Pyralidae	Serious pests in flood-prone areas in late transplanted main season rice.	72.25 CW/m ² on 24 Aug 1981 transplanting.
Grasshopper, 1980–82 <i>Oxya japonica</i> Thunberg	Acrididae	Major pest. Population increases as season advances.	3.0 GH/5 sweeps on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
Rice bug, 1980–82 <i>Leprocorisa oratorius</i> (Fab.)	Alydidae	Major pest. Population increases as season advances.	1.0 RB/5 sweeps on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
<i>Cletus</i> sp.	Coreidae		
Whorl maggot, 1980–83 <i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	Ephydriidae	Major pest in early and main season rice.	13.96% tiller infestation 15 DT on 1 Jun 1982 transplanting.
Planthoppers, 1980–83 <i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	Delphacidae	Major pests in early paddy only.	407.25 WBPH/m ² 45 DT on 15 Apr 1982 transplanting.
<i>Sogatodes pusanus</i> (Dist.)	Delphacidae		
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Delphacidae		
Nursery thrips, 1980–83 <i>Stenchaetothrips biformis</i> (Bagnall)	Thripidae	Major pest of main season nursery.	179.5 nymphs/5 sweeps 15 DT on 1 Aug 1982 sown nursery.
Greenhorned caterpillar, 1980–82 <i>Melanitis leda</i> Linn.	Nymphalidae	Major pest early in the main season.	2.5 GC/5 sweeps on 14 Jul 1981 transplanting.
Ear-cutting caterpillar, 1982 <i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walk)	Noctuidae	Sporadic pest late in the rice season.	10.9 immature insects/hill on Oct 1982 planting of RCM3.

^a DH = deadhearts, SS = silvershoots, GLH = green leafhopper, LR = leafroller, CW = caseworm, GH = grasshopper, KB = rice bug, DT = days after transplanting, WBPH = whitebacked planthopper, GC = greenhorned caterpillar. The data show peak activity of the pest on P33 at the ICAR Complex farm at Sangaipat. SS and LR are average of 6 observations; CW, GH, GLH, KB, and HC are average of 5 observations at 15-d interval, starting from 15 DT.

damaged Jul and Aug nurseries in valleys, but not in the foothills.

In 1980, whorl maggot in the main season and whitebacked planthopper in

early rice were abundant. The whitebacked planthopper seriously damaged early rice in 1983, perhaps because of unusually heavy rains and flooding. □

A meadow grasshopper *Conocephalus longipennis* (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae) predator of rice yellow stem borer (YSB) egg masses

P. C. Pantua, research assistant, and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, IRR I

Experiments to determine the egg parasitization incidence of YSB by taping egg masses to plants in the field revealed a high level of predation by an unknown insect.

Suspected predators were collected and caged with potted rice plants laden with stem borer egg masses. Adults of a meadow grasshopper, *Conocephalus longipennis* (Haan), produced identical predation symptoms as those found in the field.

Subsequent field trials using marked egg masses showed predation ranged from 17 to 65% over the sampling dates, with an overall average of 46% (see table). □

Rate of predation of *Scirpophaga incertulas* egg masses by *Conocephalus longipennis*, IRR I, 1980–81.

Date egg masses were exposed	Egg masses exposed (no.)	Predation (%)
6 Nov 1980	24	17
28 Nov 1980	32	25
7 Jan 1981	72	65
14 Jan 1981	24	45
17 Sep 1981	28	46
28 Sep 1981	40	60
9 Oct 1981	52	65

Incidence of brown planthopper (BPH) and white fly in Nigeria

M. S. Alam, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Oyo Road, P. M. B. 5320, Ibadan, Nigeria

In Mar and Apr 1983, BPH *Nilaparvata maеander* Fennah caused hopperburn in two rice fields at Ibadan, Nigeria. This is the first report of hopperburn caused by *N. maеander* in Africa. Some of the affected cultivars were TOs 5262, TOs 6860, TOx 1727-B, TOx 1812-B, TOg 6344, TOg 6399, and TOg 6745.

Mind bugs *Cyrtorhinus menanops* Reuter and *Tytthus parviceps* Reuter are

predators of eggs of this insect.

N. maeander is found only in Africa. It was first observed by Fennah (1958) in Sudan and French Guinea. Later, Critchley (1977) observed the insect in Ibadan. In Sep 1983 the insect was observed in Badeggi, at a research station of the National Cereal Research Institute.

N. maeander is a potential pest of rice in Africa.

The white fly *Aelurocybotus indicus* David and Subramaniam was found in Senegal, Upper Volta, Nigeria, and Mauritania by Williams and Dips (1981). White fly is an important rice pest in some West African countries. From Feb to Apr

1983, irrigated rice from seedling to maturity at Ibadan was infested. When infestation was high, black sooty mold developed on the leaves, which eventually withered and died. Seriously affected cultivars were TOs 6865, TOs 5827, and TOx 891-212-2-102-1-1. □

Hopperburn caused by whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

S. S. Saini, Plant Protection Officer,
Central Plant Protection Station,
Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine,
and Storage, Pathankot 145001,
Punjab, India

WBPH (*Sogatella furcifera* Horvath) population buildup, with 15-35 insects/hill, began the first week of Sep 1983 and reached epidemic levels of 200 to 500

Area and extent of damage by WBPH at different localities in 1983 kharif in the Punjab.

District	Block	Villages affected (no.)	Area infested (ha)	Level of infestation
Patiala	Patiala	7	64	Severe
	Sirhind	29	480	Very severe
	Bhunerheri	5	36	Moderate
	Bassi Pathana	14	172	Severe
	Naba		48	Moderate
Rupar	Chamkaur Sahib	10	200	Very severe
	Total	69	1000	

insects/hill by 20 Sep. About 1,000 ha of rice in the Punjab were hopperburned. PR106 was most seriously damaged, with

10-40% grain yield reduction. Area and level of infestation are given in the table. □

Nomenclature changes for some rice arthropods

A. T. Barrion, senior research assistant,
and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist,
Entomology Department, IRRI

Seed bugs

In a recent review of the seed bug genus *Stollia* Ellenrieder, *Eusarcoris* Hahn became synonymized by *Stollia* (Hsieh et al 1977. A handbook for the determination of the Chinese Hemiptera-Heteroptera). Therefore, the correct names of the species formerly under *Eusarcoris* are

- Stollia capitatus* (Distant)
- Stollia guttiger* (Thunberg)
- Stollia montivagus* (Distant)
- Stollia parvus* (Distant)
- Stollia ventralis* (Westwood)

Mole crickets

The revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets redefined the distribution of *Grylotalpa africana* Palisot de Beauvois. Townsend stated that *G. africana* is confined to Africa and does not occur in Australia or Asia (Townsend, B. C. 1983. A revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets, Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.), Entomol. 46(2): 183). *Grylotalpa orientalis* Burmeister now replaces

G. africana in Asia. The correct name for the Asian mole cricket is *Grylotalpa orientalis* Burmeister.

Larval parasites

Mason (1981) reclassified the subfamily Microgastrinae that contains important parasitic genera – *Apanteles* and *Microgaster* – and split *Apanteles* into several new genera. Thereafter, *Apanteles* became synonymized by *Cotesia*. The correct names for the stem borer parasites *A. flavipes* (Cameron) and *A. ruficrus* Haliday are now *Cotesia flavipes* Cameron and *Cotesia ruficrus* (Haliday).

In the same reclassification, *Apanteles schoenobii* Wilkinson became the type of a new genus *Exoryza* Mason and therefore, its valid name is *Exoryza schoenobii* (Wilkinson). Similarly, *Microgaster russatus* Haliday was designated type of *Hygroplitis* Thomson. Its correct name now is *Hygroplitis russatus* (Haliday).

Pupal parasite

Joseph et al (1973) studied the oriental *Brachymeria* and reported that *Brachymeria lasus* (Walker, 1841) and *B. obscurata* (Walker, 1874) were conspecific. *B. lasus* (Walker) was published 33 yr earlier than the latter and is, therefore, the correct name for both species.

Breeding methods for Pipunculidae (Diptera), endoparasites of leafhoppers

S. Huq, assistant professor, Entomology Department, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Pipunculid larvae are endoparasites of several Hornoptera families, especially Cicadellidae and Delphacidae, many of which are serious rice pests. We raised *Pipunculus campestris* Ltr., *Eudorylas subterminalis* Collin, and *Tomosvaryella sylvatica* Meig. in captivity at the Zoological Institute, West Berlin.

The breeding box measured 45 × 30 × 20 cm. The lid and two opposing sides were covered with a fine-gauge mesh to facilitate air flow. The two other sides were covered with glass. One glass side could be opened and closed. In the bottom of the box was a round 11-cm-diameter hole through which a potted host plant was inserted (see figure). The box was kept dry and clean to limit fungal infection of the emergent parasitic larvae.

Adult *Euscelis incisus* (Kib.), a species of cicadellid leafhopper (GLH) parasitized by the Pipunculidae species were collected by sweep net during summer and fall 1976 to 1980 from different